
THE ROLE OF STYLISTICS IN JOURNALISTIC TEXT AS A SOCIAL ACTION

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ABSTRACT

The article discusses the interdisciplinary nature of journalism as a sphere of scientific knowledge, establishes the problematic field of integrating journalistic research with discourse analysis of the media, defines the ontology of such interaction, and reveals the binding role of stylistics in the study of linguistic fact as a social activity.

Keywords: *journalism, discourse analysis, linguistics, information technology, practical knowledge, theoretical knowledge, cultural value.*

Introduction

Journalism as a system of scientific ideas is increasingly resorting to attempts to get involved in the problematic field of other sciences. On this occasion, the methodological remarks of some scientists are fair: “We draw a lot from historians, philologists, philosophers, but we give them little. Representatives of other sciences do not want or cannot take advantage of the achievements of the theory of journalism” [Panel discussions... 2013]. Indeed, for now, we can only talk about intentions to look at related areas of research.

The current situation is natural and has epistemological roots. The view of journalism as a science caused (and still causes) skepticism among many. The reason for this is the vague and, unfortunately, not exactly established ontological status of this science, which apparently lies in the trinity of journalism as a professional activity, the methodology of creativity and the shaky sphere of scientific knowledge.

Journalism and information society

In the era of the information society, the problem of recognizing journalism's right to theoretical and methodological, i.e. scientific, relevance seems paradoxical. The emergence of information technologies that blew up the world and systematically "transformed it into a virtual one" caused precisely by the technological nature of journalism: the main driving force of the post-industrial society - computers - brought

information technologies to a new level, like once television, and even earlier - printing. IT covers all areas of creation, transmission, storage, and perception of information. The professional role of a journalist is changing: from a recent agitator and propagandist, he reincarnates into a communicative leader whose mobility forms the content environment and subtly influences the mass consciousness. The methods of journalistic creativity are undergoing qualitative changes towards an even greater technology of the process, on the one hand, and an increase in the individual principle, on the other. Opinion journalism is emerging: today we are talking about the personification of the modern journalist, as well as the media-centricity of the world. All this takes place against the background of integrated teachings, the connecting link of which is information as a tool for cognizing reality.

However, against the background of ongoing processes in practical journalism, theory often does not anticipate events but is only a belated reaction to what is happening. Journalism theorists have been forced to take for granted the digitization that has given rise to media convergence. Now, this is leading to a conceptual transformation of editorial offices in organizational and managerial, production and technological, legal, methodological, and educational terms. So, Professor E. L. Vartanova writes: “In media research, we find a clash of fundamental and applied nature, analyzing practice, we do not always create a theory. Using an interdisciplinary approach, we isolate narrow problems. And often the most profound judgments about the state of the media come from industry practitioners, not academic researchers. This emphasizes the fact that our science is not yet very structured and does not clearly see its boundaries” [Vartanova 2013].

Mass consciousness in adapting information

Journalism adapts scientific and practical knowledge to the mass consciousness in order to adopt the latter behavior patterns, political preferences, cultural values, morality, ethics, and aesthetics. The media cultivate the ideology of the development of society, journalism penetrates into all spheres of people's lives, its beginning is based on contiguity, and inter-disciplinarity, and it is deeply historical. A look at the writings of ancient authors confirms this. Journalism as a sphere of scientific knowledge goes back to Aristotle's classification of sciences, which reigned supreme in European culture up to Fr. Bacon. For Aristotle, this is the third area of theoretical knowledge - creativity, where rhetoric belongs as particular scientific knowledge. Due to various circumstances (primarily due to the fall of slave-owning democracy), rhetoric at the end of antiquity falls into decay and turns into a scholastic discipline,

permeated with the cataloging of techniques and the nomenclature of tropes and figures. By the 4th c. rhetoric coincides with the concept of literature. The theory of finding material (inventio) in a literary work is being revived, in the competence of rhetoric until the 13th century, including any material about which the author should have had a clear and rational idea (intellectio).

Medieval rhetoric preserved (and passed on to modern journalism) the doctrine of the triune task: docere, movere, delectare (inform/teach, induce/influence/influence, and entertain). In Italy, this finds a brilliant refraction in the theory of three styles, developed at one time by Aristotle and acting at different times in all European countries (in Russia it embodied in the theory of M.V. Lomonosov). A new classicism is emerging in rhetoric: every speech must either prove (low style), or paint (medium), or captivate (high). In the XVIII century. rhetoric loses the status of science and dissolves into stylistics, in which, along with other functional styles, journalistic styles are singled out, where a journalist is given an arsenal of speech means of informing, influencing, and establishing contact in order to develop a perlocutionary effect (persuasive or entertaining). Today, the information product is considered a social action directly related to local and temporal correlation, as a phenomenon of communication and cognition.

Journalism in the modern understanding

Journalism in the modern understanding of science is based on three Aristotelian pillars: philosophy, politics, and rhetoric. Subsequently, the classifications of sciences were concretized, supplemented, and detailed. However, journalism did not find a nominative designation in them. Today, this is reflected in the contiguity of journalism in such "established" areas as history, philology, political science, and sociology.

And yet, the awareness in the world of the need to cultivate scientific interests in the field of journalism is obvious, as evidenced by the research of the International Association for Media and Communication Studies, although here, according to E. L. Vartanova, “a unified approach has not been formulated and there is no common paradigm.” “We, media researchers,” writes E. L. Vartanova, “do not have the “Einstein formula”, which is recognized by everyone. Although most scientists agree that the key questions were developed by academic schools in the United States, in Western Europe the most important theoretical approaches were formulated in the USSR. At the same time, Western Europe provides a fairly wide range of directions - Scandinavian, British, Francophone, and German-centric. And even a few small

countries, such as the Netherlands, Belgium, Switzerland, and Finland, according to the guru of the theory of mass communication D. McQuail, have made quite a significant contribution to scientific theory.” In the end, the conclusion is summed up: “Today, the Russian science of journalism and the media requires updating, modernizing and integrating both existing paradigms and those that we had. Moreover, it requires the integration of new fields, new realities that arise around it. A theoretical and, as a result, an educational breakthrough is needed, because our academic theory must determine the place, functions and roles of journalism in modern society” [Vartanova 2013]. This becomes more relevant for modern society, when the development of strategies and goals for the functioning of the media, the behavior and values of publications, television and radio channels, Internet sources, and individual journalists have an impact on the development of the whole society more than circulars, more actively than fiction.

Points between journalism and other sciences

There are many points of contact between journalism and other sciences, which is especially clearly expressed in its cognitive essence. The prospect of such research is obvious. The integrating beginning of the interpenetration of the interests of journalism and related sciences, of course, is the discourse analysis of the media, where the media text is presented as a phenomenon containing a wide range of cognitive, pragmatic pointers to the structure of society, social and spiritual and moral priorities of its development.

In this regard, in line with modern media research, the evolution of knowledge in the vector direction is of great interest: text-style-discourse.

The journalistic text acts as a kind of barometer of changes in the life of society, and promptly reflects them. Due to extra-linguistic influences (speed of distribution, mass character, etc.), evolutionary shifts in the syntagmatic of linguistic signs can be traced in the media text, and the paradigmatic possibilities of the language are creatively realized. A journalist, creating an author's text, decodes reality.

The structural units of the language, entering into systemic relations with each other, acquire a functional coloring, revealing the possibility of the manifestation of a linguistic sign in the linguistic picture of the world. If the coherence and integrity of the text as a structural unit of speech attracted the attention of researchers at the beginning of the 20th century, then the text as a fragment of reality is of great interest to modern researchers. It can be said that the study of linguistic units over the past two centuries has evolved from the study of the word to the study of a complex

syntactic whole (super-phrasal unity, prose stanza), which ultimately led to the main interest of linguistics of the twentieth century. Today, the style of the beginning of this century is undergoing significant changes. An activist approach to the text as a communication tool is being implemented, special attention is paid to the extra-linguistic factors of the linguistic personality of the author and the addressee “outside the text”. This gives the right to talk about communicative style. In this case, the role of stylistics in the formation of a new communicative-cognitive linguistic paradigm becomes obvious. The change of the latter was destined in the concept of M. M. Bakhtin: “The style in most cases appears as the style of indoor craftsmanship and ignores the social life of the word outside the artist’s studio, in the expanses of squares, streets, cities and villages, social groups, generations, eras. Stylistics does not deal with the living word, but with its histological preparation, with the abstract linguistic word in the service of the artist’s individual skill. But even these individual and directed overtones of style, divorced from the main social ways of life of the word, inevitably receive a flat and abstract interpretation and cannot be studied in organic unity with the semantic spheres of the work” [Bakhtin 1975: 73]. Nihilism in relation to traditional stylistics is growing, which has ontological roots.

Stylistics and linguistic semiotics in journalism

Stylistics is close to linguistic semiotics and pragmatics, the theory of speech influence, and the theory of linguistic variation. However, with the tools of aesthetically marked speech, she could not help but find an outlet in the study of opposing variants of linguistic expression, where the same extra-linguistic content is fixed, but at the same time it is additionally reported on the speaker’s attitude to the communicative situation, to the content of the statement, to the addressee and to himself. Stylistic variants are considered from the point of view of their formation, scope of use and principles of selection, depending on the goals of the speech situation. The stylist studies holistic speech formations and, undoubtedly, goes to the level of the text. In this vein, a scientific understanding of the text as discourse is gradually being formed.

In the mid-1970s, in linguistics, the text is rethought as a communicative process, so linguistics moves from a static approach to a so-called dynamic, procedural approach. For example, the journalistic text in this approximation occupies a special place and has research priorities in line with discourse analysis, which is systematically included in the scientific biography of linguistic stylistics.

Today it becomes obvious that other trends are emerging in modern style than in the 20th century. “The significance of stylistics is also found in an in-depth special study of the problems of interaction between linguistic and extra-linguistic, including, for example, the problem of the connection between language/speech and thinking, the influence of various social factors on speech and its typology. Note that with the use of stylostatistical methods, it is possible to quite convincingly prove the influence of certain specific extra-linguistic factors on the style of speech, and at the same time on certain of its features” [Kozhina 2012: 63].

Conclusion

The subjective idea of the semantic coherence of discourse can be determined by the fact that such knowledge should be effectively organized into special clusters that contain specific information publicly available to society about the stereotyped variant of an episode. A native speaker has an important ability to determine what the text is written about, he is able to detect and summarize quite accurately complex information strategies of the message, activate the model of the real situation, which is formed from elements of social experience, other information sources, derive a general thematic structure from a specific situational model. However, he is unable to predict the style of a particular person who creates the text, the motivations that control the actions and attitudes of the author. Knowledge, beliefs, attitudes, situational awareness, and all other types of general information are acquired, used, and changed in various social contexts. Thus, journalism as a set of functional texts and a form of discourse appears primarily in the event aspect, as “speech is a purposeful social action” and appears in the discourse model as a sphere of specific sociocultural activity based on scenario structures developed by the practice of communication, the interaction of society. with the media.

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